

Libraries In The Digital Era: An Overview On The Role Of ICT And Emerging Technologies

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Abstract: Libraries are the heart of the institution, where all information of that institution is kept in an organized way and accessed by the users. Every sector implements Information and communication technology (ICT) in this developing generation to automate themselves. As a result, libraries must adopt ICT to stay relevant to the generation. Libraries have to automate their operations and services using various ICT products. Today, libraries are automated and digitalized using digital library software, which benefits users in multiple ways. Through the use of ICT, libraries modernize various tasks that enhance efficiency. New technologies provide diverse channels and sources of information to the users. This paper discusses the different dimensions of emerging technology in libraries and the application of information and communication technology.

Index Terms - Library in the modern era, Roles of ICT in libraries, Innovative Technologies in Libraries, Use and benefits of using ICT, Digital Library, Automation, Emerging technologies.

I. INTRODUCTION

A library is a structured collection of information and knowledge in the form of library materials such as books, journals, and newspapers, which are accessed and utilized by the users as per their needs. Libraries serve as essential institutions for the preservation and dissemination of knowledge. In addition to physical materials, modern libraries update themselves by using ICT. Integrating information and communication technology in libraries has revolutionized how information is accessed, stored, and disseminated. To enhance the user experience, modern libraries adopt digital tools, online databases, and automated systems. This shift has transformed traditional libraries into dynamic hubs of learning, information dissemination, and innovation, supporting education, research, and lifelong learning in a digital world.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Arora, J. (2025) conducted a study entitled “Library2.0: Innovative Technologies for Building Libraries of Tomorrow.” This research paper deals with the concept of Library 2.0 and its purpose and application to bring revolutionary changes in libraries. It also discusses the implications of these revolutionary technologies. This research examines the impact of emerging technology in the library, and the study concluded that Library 2.0 has reshaped library collections, making them more interesting and interactive.

Venkatesha (2024) conducted a study entitled “**An Overview of the Role of Modern Libraries in Current Society**”. This research paper explains the role of the modern library in current society, which the majority of people associate with library books, while this is true, books have recently taken new forms such as e-books and other online materials. This study highlights how libraries serve as a gateway to knowledge, culture, and social development.

Hoque, A. (2023) conducted a study entitled “**Libraries in the Digital Age: the importance of ICT in enhancing value-added library services**”. This research paper explains the importance of ICT in Libraries and elaborates on the need to adopt ICT to remain relevant and provide value-added services to users.

Gul, S., and Bano, S. (2019) conducted a study entitled “**Smart Libraries: An Emerging and Innovative Technological Habitat of the 21st Century.**” This study discusses the emerging and innovative technologies that integrate to form smart libraries and confirms that smart libraries are becoming smarter with emerging smart technologies. The implementation of these technologies has bridged traditional to modern libraries.

Ogar, C. E., and Dushu, T. Y. (2018) conducted a study entitled “**Transforming library and information services delivery using innovation technologies.**” This study focused on measuring the impact of information technology on libraries and identified the paradigm shift in libraries and information services as a direct consequence of innovative technologies.

Bhoi, N.K. (2017) conducted a study entitled “**Use of Information and Communication Technology and Library Operation**”. This study explains the library housekeeping operation using information and communication technology. In this paper, the author discusses the different dimensions of ICTs and the awareness of technology in the library.

Mittal, A. (2016) conducted a study entitled “**Emerging Technologies and Their Impact on the Libraries**”. The main objective of this study is to examine the applications of new technology in different areas of the library, changes in the library with emerging technology, areas where new technology applies, and problems in implementing new technologies.

III. OBJECTIVE:

- To analyse the roles and benefits of using Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in libraries.
- To provide a comprehensive idea of new innovative and emerging technologies in the libraries.

IV. Information and Communication Technology:

ICT combines a broad range of technologies for Information capture, collection, processing, management, indexing, storage, and dissemination. ICT includes hardware and software that provide devices like computers and their operating systems, as well as a transmission channel that enables data transfer through wired or wireless networks like the Internet and satellite communication. ICT transfers how individuals and organizations communicate and function by facilitating faster information access and exchange. However, ICT introduces some challenges like data security, individual and organizational privacy, and the digital divide. ICT transformed the role of libraries, enhancing the way libraries organize, manage, manipulate, and disseminate information. ICT enables information to be accessible online remotely and improves search capabilities through the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC). Additionally, Libraries use ICT to provide services like Virtual reference assistants, cloud services, institutional repositories, online learning and training, information kiosks, etc. Overall, ICT allows libraries to evolve from traditional to dynamic libraries and digital knowledge hubs.

Modern library: Modern library goes beyond traditional books and traditional library housekeeping operation, which is dynamic. Modern libraries merge technology and resources to meet the evolving needs of today's users. Modern libraries serve services like OPAC, e-books, online databases, and multimedia collection, allowing users to access 24*7 remotely. Ultimately modern libraries are knowledge dissemination organizations that bridge the gap between traditional information sources and the digital age, promoting lifelong learning.

Library 2.0: Library 2.0 refers to the evolution of libraries in the digital age, emerging technology, and user-centered approaches to meet the changing needs of current library patrons, which emphasizes the integration of web tools, social media, and innovative and interactive features to enhance user access to information. The key focus of Library 2.0 is improving the user's experience by making information more accessible, interactive, and personalized.

Roles of ICT in Modern Libraries:

1. **Automation of Library operation:** ICT introduces Library Management Systems (LMS) that enable libraries to automate their housekeeping operations like acquisition, cataloguing, circulation, management, and serial controls. LMS also provides an Online Public Access Catalogue that allows users to search and check the availability of resources. The best example of LMS is “Koha”, an open-access integrated library management software designed to automate and manage the library’s daily operations and administrative tasks.
2. **Digital Library and Institutional Repository:** ICT provides a facility for the creation of a Digital Library using different digital repository software like D-Space, E-Prints, and Greenstone, where information is archived and accessed remotely.
3. **Database:** Using ICT, users can access different types of e-resources such as different types of academic journals, research databases, and different digital content through DOAJ (Directory of Open Access Journals), JSTORE (), Open DOAR (Directory of Open Access Repository), Scopus, Web of Science, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar, etc.
4. **Cloud Services:** Cloud computing is an additional feature of ICT by using which Libraries store Information on the cloud making it accessible from any location. Different examples of cloud service providers globally are Amazon Web Services (AWS), Microsoft Azure, Google Cloud, Alibaba, IBM Cloud, Tencent Cloud, Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI), Huawei Cloud, Dell Technologies Cloud, and Cisco Cloud Solutions.
5. **Online learning and training:** Libraries often use ICT to offer online learning, training sessions, and webinars to enhance the user’s research and information literacy skills.
6. **Virtual reference services:** One of the various types of library services is reference service, which involves interaction between the user and a reference librarian to fulfil the user's needs. ICT allows libraries to offer online reference services by email and live chat with librarians, helping users get assistance without physically visiting the library.
7. **Library Websites:** Libraries use their websites to provide information about their collections, services, rules, and regulations, which are linked to their parent organization.

The roles of information and communication technology in the library, starting from housekeeping operations to different extension services, are very crucial. ICT in libraries increases efficiency, accessibility, and user satisfaction by providing digital services and new ways to build relationships with information and knowledge.

V. Innovative Technologies Used in Modern Libraries:

Libraries and information centers are where information is archived and stored in an organized way. To improve access, enhance user experience, and streamline library operation using various innovative technologies.

1. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning:

- i. AI-powered chatbots assist users in searching for resources on the internet and also help and guide them in searching for information in library resources.
- ii. Voice-operated Information kiosk for searching information.
- iii. Machine Learning algorithms analyse user behaviour to recommend personalized reading materials.
- iv. AI-powered virtual assistant answers FAQs and provides research guidance 24/7.

2. Internet of Things (IoT):

- i. Smart shelves with RFID tags for inventory management and location tracking. Also, with RFID libraries, you can monitor and track records of library materials. RFID enables a self-checkout system which improves user convenience.
- ii. QR codes to link to digital content, event details, or other resources. Users can scan QR codes with their phones to quickly access additional information.
- iii. IoT enables Heating, Ventilation, and Air conditioning (HVAC) systems for automated climate control, ensuring optimal temperature and humidity to preserve books and create a comfortable environment for library materials and users.
- iv. Light sensors can adjust lighting based on occupancy or time of day, saving energy.
- v. IoT enhances the security and safety of libraries by using security cameras and early fire and water sensor detection systems.

3. Blockchain Technology:

- i. Blockchain technology can streamline digital rights management by providing a secure, transparent, and immutable record of ownership and licensing information.
- ii. Blockchain could record the history of an item, including its previous owner, which helps to track the provenance of rare or valuable materials.
- iii. Libraries can create systems that protect users' privacy while maintaining transparency, users could have more control over their data and borrowing history.

4. Digital preservation technology:

- i. Tools like LOCKSS (Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) and CLOCKSS (Controlled Lots of Copies Keep Stuff Safe) to safeguard digital assets and historical materials.
- ii. Bitstream preservation ensures that the exact binary representation of the digital file is preserved over time, which maintains the original file without altering it to another format.

5. Virtual Reality:

- i. Researchers visualize complex concepts for better understanding, like critical operations to astronomical events. VR experiences include virtual museum tours, historical simulations, and immersive educational content.

6. Cloud-based library systems:

- i. Cloud computing integrates library operations and services from one centralized platform, such as cloud-based software, to manage cataloguing, user services, inventory, and circulation.

7. 3D Printing:

- i. Using 3D printing, patrons can design and print prototype models like historical artifacts, and scientific models.

8. Augmented Reality:

- i. Using AR technologies to revolutionize the library educational experience, AR can bring physical books to life by overlaying additional content such as videos, animation, or interactive Maps.

VI. Benefits of Using ICT in Libraries:

Libraries are beneficiaries of information and communication technology in various aspects such as ICT use to improve access to library resources, automate library operations, preservation of library materials, data management, and others.

1. **Improved access to resources:** Information and communication technology allow library users to access a wide range of information resources by using the internet, such as different types of digital content like e-books, journals, digital databases, and multimedia content, also ICT makes it easier for users to find and retrieve information.
2. **Automate library operations:** Library management systems automate library operations like Acquisition, circulation, cataloguing, and management of library materials, improving efficiency and minimizing human error, leading to increased accuracy.
3. **Online services:** Users can access library resources remotely through an Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC), database, and digital collections. Services like e-book borrowing, online reservation, and virtual reference enhance accessibility.
4. **Information retrieval:** ICT tools such as advanced search engines and indexing systems, make it easier for users to find relevant information quickly, even from a large information collection.
5. **Cost efficiency:** ICT enables libraries to reduce costs in various aspects, such as lower maintenance costs, reduction in print resources, and decreased staffing costs.
6. **Library networks:** ICT facilitates collaboration between libraries by creating networks for resource sharing between them. This network allows the exchange of information between member libraries.
7. **Digital preservation:** ICT can facilitate the digitalization of rare historic materials, preserving them for future generations while ensuring continuous access.
8. **User engagement:** other extension services are provided by the library for user engagement such as online forums, social media, virtual events, and weaners by using ICT.
9. **Digital literacy:** libraries provide users with opportunities to develop essential skills, which are increasingly important in education and work, by integrating ICT.
10. **Data management:** libraries can use ICT tools to collect data and analyse them, helping to improve services, and manage resources better.

The integration of ICT tools in libraries enhances service delivery, enhances access to information, and improves efficacy, benefiting the trinity of the library.

VII. Disadvantage of ICT in Libraries:

New technologies may have several disadvantages in libraries, which include

1. **Loss of Physical Library Collections:** Modern libraries are prioritizing digital resources over physical resources, which can lead to a reduction in physical book collection. Due to this, there is a risk that some rare physical materials may not be preserved or digitalised, which could be lost or damaged over time.
2. **Environmental Impact of Technology:** ICT can contribute to environmental impact through an increase in energy consumption. Additionally, older technological equipment can become e-waste when replaced. Maintaining a vast digital collection may have a larger carbon emission than a traditional library.
3. **Overload of Information and Digital Content:** Modern libraries provide a vast collection of digital resources, which leads to an explosion of digital content, and patrons might suffer during locating information that need. Modern libraries provide access to a wide range of content but not all digital content is high quality, this poses a risk to patrons who rely on library resources.
4. **Increased Reliance on Technology:** Modern libraries depend on technology for their housekeeping operations and providing access to information. System failure, such as server crashes, can halt operations. Over-reliance on technology might also result in fewer opportunities for patrons to develop critical information literacy skills through personal guidance from librarians.

5. **Digital Divide and Access Inequality:** Not all library patrons have access to the internet, modern devices, or the digital literacy skills required to use online resources effectively, this digital divide can disproportionately affect underserved or rural communities, elderly individuals, and low-income families.

VIII. CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, traditional libraries are undergoing a transformative shift towards digital and automated libraries, driven by new technologies from RFID to Artificial Intelligence and Augmented reality. These shifts are reshaping the library operations and services provided by the libraries. Technologies streamline the library operation, making it more efficient and accessible, and also expand the scope of learning and research. As libraries adopt these technological innovations, they are positioning themselves as a future-ready institution that can meet the evolving needs of a digital society. The future libraries will be defended by their ability to adapt to technological advances while staying true to their foundational purpose of serving. But every good thing also has a bad side, due to the transformation of traditional libraries to modern libraries, a traditional library can be considered “Dead” because the eider spread availability of digital content through the internet and electronic databases has significantly reduced the need for physical books in a traditional library, causing a decline in foot patrons and reliance on scholarly physical collections, forcing traditional libraries to adapt and incorporate digital resource to remain relevant.

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